

Appendix 5 AMIA Meeting Content

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Program Schedule

Depending on your settings, sessions with multiple presentations included will not export properly to Outlook (Posters, Oral Presentations). We advise manually blocking the time for these particular sessions in your Outlook calendar.

LB01: Late Breaking Session - Moving Beyond Performative Action: Getting Real about Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion

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Monday, Nov 16, 2020 2:00 PM - 3:30 PM

Session Credits: 1.50

Description

The AMIA Board recently created the AMIA Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) Task Force to advise AMIA on specific, actionable steps to further address matters of racial diversity, equity and inclusion to ensure future success for both AMIA and the informatics field. This late-breaking session will discuss how diversity, equity and inclusion are essential for advancing scientific excellence (including health disparities), and how it supports AMIA's new 2020-2025 Strategic Plan. Presenters represent education, research, industry and practice and will share their perspective briefly, allowing time for participant interaction during the session. Objectives include listening to the community, sharing expected outcomes of the work, and disseminating plans for member engagement. Attend the session to find out how to volunteer on DEI teams planning a range of activities from leadership pipelines, education and outreach.

Speaker(s)

Patricia Dykes
[View Profile](#)

Tiffani Bright
[View Profile](#)

Rodney Cohen
[View Profile](#)

David Asai
[View Profile](#)

Rosemary Ventura
[View Profile](#)

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Program Schedule

The times listed are Eastern Time.

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S38: Panel - JAMIA as a Voice for Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion in Biomedical and Health Informatics, Health Care, and Society

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Wednesday, Mar 24, 2021 1:30 PM - 3:00 PM

Session Credits: 1.50

Description

In this session, the JAMIA Editor-in-Chief, as well as an Associate Editor, Guest Editor, and two authors reflect on the role of JAMIA as one of AMIA's journals to foster diversity, equity, and inclusion in AMIA, biomedical and health informatics and society.

Suzanne Bakken, PhD, RN, FAAN, FACMI, FIAHSI, Columbia University, Editor-in-Chief, will provide an overview of JAMIA's efforts and serve as the moderator for the panel.

Panelists

Tiffany Veinot, PhD, University of Michigan, Guest Editor and Editorial Board Member, will discuss the intersection of health equity and informatics, as reflected in a 2019 special double issue of JAMIA that she led along with Jessica Ancker, PhD, FACMI (Associate Editor) highlighting key challenges and important next steps.

Tina Hernandez Boussard, PhD, FACMI, Stanford University, Associate Editor, will discuss the importance of transparency in medical AI reporting and standards to support such reporting as exemplified in her 2020 JAMIA paper.

Matt Pantell, MD, MS, University of California, San Francisco, will discuss the need for a sub-field of informatics that he and his JAMIA co-authors call "social informatics" because of its tight integration of social determinants of health.

Nir Menachemi, PhD, MPH, Indiana University, will address diversity and inclusion in the education pipeline by summarizing a study, published in JAMIA, that examined graduation rates and future positions of under-represented minorities in biomedical informatics PhD programs.

Panel Multi-track Session

Speaker(s)

Dr. Tina Hernandez-Boussard

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Dr. Tiffany Veinot

[View Profile](#)

Dr. Suzanne Bakken

[View Profile](#)

Dr. Matt Pantell

[View Profile](#)

Dr. Nir Menachemi

Program Schedule

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Depending on your settings, sessions with multiple presentations included will not export properly to Outlook (Posters, Presentations). We advise manually blocking the time for these particular sessions in your Outlook calendar.

S32: Panel - The Journey to a Diverse AMIA Board of Directors: Why You Matter!

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Thursday, May 20, 2021 11:30 AM - 12:30 PM

Session Credits: 1.00

Description

In June 2020, the American Medical Informatics Association (AMIA) Board of Directors unanimously approved the creation of the AMIA Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) Task Force to advise AMIA on specific, actionable steps to further address matters of racial diversity, equity, and inclusion. A diverse Board of Directors is central to advancing DEI in AMIA. In this session, current Directors will discuss the importance of a diverse Board for AMIA, what Board service entails, and the Board self-nomination process. Several Board members will also share their personal paths to Board membership to encourage a broad range of AMIA members to self-nominate for the Board. This session will also include discussion with conference participants about Board diversity.

Speaker(s)

Dr. Tiffani Bright

[View Profile](#)

William Brown III

[View Profile](#)

S. Trent Rosenbloom

[View Profile](#)

Patricia Dykes

[View Profile](#)

Gretchen Purcell Jackson

[View Profile](#)

How Will AMIA Lead? An Environmental Scan of Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Activities within the Healthcare and Health IT Space

Tiffani J. Bright, PhD, FACMI¹, Carolyn Petersen, MS, MBI, FAMIA², Karen Wang, MD, MHS³, Clair Kronk, PhD⁴, Patricia C. Dykes, PhD, RN, FAAN, FACMI⁵

¹IBM Watson Health, Cambridge, MA; ²Mayo Clinic, Rochester, MN; ³Yale School of Medicine, New Haven, CT; ⁴University of Cincinnati School of Medicine, Cincinnati, OH; ⁵Brigham and Women’s Hospital, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA

Introduction

In June 2020, the AMIA Board of Directors established the Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) Task Force to advise AMIA on specific, actionable steps addressing matters of racial diversity, equity, and inclusion for strategic planning. An immediate charge of the DEI Task Force was to conduct an environmental scan of DEI activities in similar associations and societies. Environmental scans are efficient for assessing how organizations have acquired data and information to establish actions but also set strategic direction¹. Objectives were to: 1) identify activities that other associations in the healthcare community were undertaking to advance DEI within their membership and the broader community; and 2) build a knowledge base on which to draw for strategic planning.

Methods

Web searches were undertaken to find organizations and societies serving health care and health information technology professionals in September 2020. During November and December 2020, content published on these organizations’ websites was reviewed and DEI-related policies/position statements and activities were captured. Policy/position statements and activities were grouped by type and purpose (e.g., policies applying to membership, professional development) and counted as a percentage of the number of organizations scanned.

Results

Figure 1. DEI Policies

The web searches identified 30 organizations: 4 health IT organizations, 1 non-profit academic research organization, and 25 healthcare professional organizations. Policy/position statements from 5 of these centered on Black, Indigenous and People of Color physicians; 2 served physicians with diverse abilities; and 1 focused on health equity for LGBTQIA+ and sexual and gender marginalized health professionals. Across the organizations, 17% had no policy/position or activity, 47% had 1–5 policies/positions and/or activities, 23% had

6–8 policies/positions and/or Activities, and 13% had at least 10 policies/positions and/or activities. The organizations surveyed in this environmental scan published policies/position statements addressing 8 topical areas (Figure 1). Table 1 presents the most common policy/position statements.

Table 1. DEI policy/position statements

Policy/ Position Type	%	Example
Diversity	53%	Diversity in Health Services Research: AH
		Establishing a Culturally Competent Masters and Doctorally Prepared Nursing Workforce: ANA
COVID-19 and Race	33%	Statement Urging HHS to Collect, Analyze, and Release COVID-19 Data on Mortality by Race & Ethnicity: NHMA
		COVID-19 Treatments Must Work for Communities of Color: NCAPIP, NHMA
Racism	20%	Statement on Addressing Racism Through Collective Action in Ob/Gyn: AOA
		Addressing and Eliminating Racism at the AAMC and Beyond: AAMC
Discrimination	20%	Discrimination in Membership Evaluation: AAFP
		Statement on Harassment, Bullying, and Discrimination: ACS

Eleven types of activities were used to promote DEI across the organizations (Figure 2). Table 2 presents the most prevalent types of DEI activities.

Figure 2. DEI Activities

Conclusion

This environmental scan found common DEI activities AMIA could implement to create a culture of inclusion and belonging for members and within the informatics profession. The findings demonstrated that there is no singular activity pursued by organizations, rather, multipronged strategies were the norm across these diverse organization. We also observed commonalities in activities across organizations that need to be explored further. The widespread activities across many similar organizations reaffirms the urgency and importance of sustained resource-committed AMIA DEI efforts. The DEI Task Force will use these findings to inform and prioritize AMIA Board recommendations and transform AMIA into the professional organization that reflects society and the communities we serve, enabling members and the broader informatics workforce to influence and lead the transformation of healthcare.

Table 3. Legend of abbreviations (abbr.)

Organization	Abbr.	Organization	Abbr.
American Academy of Emergency Medicine	AAEM	Association of Medical Professionals with Hearing Losses	AMPHL
American Academy of Family Physicians	AAFP	American Medical Women's Association	AMWA
Association of American Indian Physicians	AAIP	American Nurses Association	ANA
Association of American Medical Colleges	AAMC	American Osteopathic Association	AOA
American Association of Nurse Practitioners	AANP	American Physical Therapy Association	APTA
American Academy of Pediatrics	AAP	College of Healthcare Information Management Executives	CHIME
American Academy of Physician Assistants	AAPA	Health Professionals Advancing LGBTQ Equality	GLMA
American College of Surgeons	ACS	National Council of Asian Pacific Islander Physicians	NCAPIP
AcademyHealth	AH	National Hispanic Medical Association	NHMA
American Hospital Association	AHA	National Medical Association	NMA
American Medical Association	AMA		

Acknowledgments. The authors thank the DEI Task Force members and AMIA staff for sharing their insights.

Learning Objectives

At completion of this activity, participants will be able to (1) Understand how the AMIA Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Task Force addressed the DEI Charge given by the AMIA Board to conduct an environmental scan.

References

1. Choo CW. Environmental scanning as information seeking and organizational learning. *Information Research*. 2001 Oct;7(1):7-1.

Table 2. Most common DEI activities

Activity Type	%	Example
Professional Education	43%	Certificate in Diversity Management: AHA
		Mid-career minority faculty leadership seminar: AAMC
Committee/Task Force	40%	DEI Committee/commission: AAEM, AAP, AAPA, AANP, ACS, AMWA, APTA, AAMC, CHIME
		Advisory committee on LGBTQ issues: AMA
Research/Survey	37%	Diversity in Medicine: Facts and Figures 2019: AAMC
		Accessibility, Inclusion, and Action in Medical Education: Lived Experiences of Learners and Physicians with Disabilities: AAMC
Professional Groups	33%	National Hispanic Leadership Agenda: NHLA
		Global Health Equity Network African American Community: HIMSS

Recommendations on Building A Sustainable AMIA Centered Around Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Practices—A Preliminary Report

Rubina Rizvi MD, PhD¹; Casey Taylor Overby PhD²; C. Erwin Johnson MD, EdM,MSc³; Tiffani J. Bright PhD, FACMI¹

¹IBM Watson Health, Cambridge, MA; ²Division of General Internal Medicine, Johns Hopkins University; ³Merck CORE, Policy Evidence Research

Introduction

The topic of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) was in the forefront of 2020. The initiatives to strengthen DEI-related structures and policies are relevant, now more than ever, both in the USA and globally. However, it is imperative that these DEI-related activities are long term and sustainable, as they come with numerous challenges that are often deep-rooted, reflecting systematic and organizational problems. To further DEI efforts, AMIA must redesign the infrastructure of the systems that delay the progression and ensure sustainability of DEI within the organization. We identify and propose a list of strategic shifts and recommendations that when incorporated into DEI practices, better equip AMIA and its leaders to manage, foster, and sustain DEI.

Methods

In the context of ‘AMIA Strategic Visioning Final Report’ (SVFR), created in July of 2020, the AMIA DEI task force (TF) created three themes and corresponding subcommittees to achieve the following three targets: (1) ‘Make AMIA Diverse’—promote and build diverse representation within the AMIA membership; (2) ‘Make AMIA Inclusive’—empower AMIA members to build an inclusive professional organization; and (3) ‘Make AMIA Sustainable’—optimize the infrastructure to sustain AMIA’s DEI development and focus. We report the work of the Make AMIA Sustainable subcommittee. Each subcommittee member (COT, RR, CEJ) independently reviewed the AMIA SVFR that illuminates specific strategic and tactical suggestions based on feedback from AMIA members and other stakeholders. Each subcommittee member created a list of strategic shifts and recommendations along with additional input from other subcommittee AMIA TF members. The Make AMIA Sustainable subcommittee met bimonthly for seven months to discuss and brainstorm ideas and learnings. All recommendations were compiled into a comprehensive document to report the goal of each proposed shift, how to implement proposed shifts, and possible outcomes. The recommendations were mapped to each subcommittee (Diverse, Inclusive, and Sustainable), along with existing AMIA committee/working groups to operationalize the recommendations. A final, full report was generated.

Results

A total of 16 unique strategic shifts were identified. Each proposed shift describes how it can be achieved, possible outcomes of each recommendation, alignment with DEI themes, and which AMIA working group can help to facilitate action. Some of the proposed shifts were applicable across more than one theme i.e., Diverse AMIA (N=5), Inclusive AMIA (N=10), and Sustainable AMIA (N=5). Key recommendations for the Governance task force (N=3) were also identified. The map of these recommendations with DEI themes and AMIA committee/working groups is illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1- Recommendations

Promote and Build the Field Diverse AMIA – SC # 1		Empower our Members Inclusive AMIA – SC # 2		Optimize Infrastructure Sustainable AMIA – SC # 3	
Recommendations (N=5)	Existing Working Group/ SC	Recommendations (N=10)	Existing Working Group/ SC	Recommendations (N=5)	Existing Working Group/SC
Begin collecting and sharing more precise, transparent data on AMIA’s members.	Member and Outreach committee	Design and introduce a new online platform.	Member and Outreach committee, Communications	Design a leadership training and mentorship program.	Education committee
Immediately begin a feasibility & business planning process to introduce a larger number of lower-cost virtual conferences.	Finance and Investment, committee, Member and Outreach committee, Working group steering committee	Design mechanisms for current members to serve as liaisons.	Communications	Reconceptualize the Working Groups.	Working group steering committee, Governance task force
Support activities/event promoting collaboration and networking.	Member and Outreach committee	Fully support the academic forum and its members.	Education committee	Take steps towards creating an AMIA Assembly, to give all members an ongoing voice in the organization’s strategy.	Member and Outreach committee, Governance task force
Highlight the DE&I topic.	Communication, Journals and publications	Support activities/event promoting collaboration and networking.	Member and Outreach committee	Develop Workforce based on DE&I principles.	Membership and Outreach, Women in AMIA
Make DE&I one of the pillars for AMIA success.	All	Create and/or open new pathways centered around DE&I.	AMIA board, Governance task force	Make DE&I one of the pillars for AMIA success.	All
		Provide autonomy and empowerment to all members. Support and provide venues to other overlooked informatics topics.	Membership and Outreach, Working group Working group steering committee, Education		
		Expand the audience.	Communications + Others		
		Highlight the DE&I topic.	Communications, Journals and publications		
		Make DE&I one of the pillars for AMIA success.	All		

Conclusion

The Make AMIA Sustainable subcommittee comprehensively identified ways that AMIA can advance, promote, and sustain a culture of inclusion and belonging through a DEI strategy. To promote, sustain and promote a culture of DEI requires interconnected and explicit DEI goals throughout the organization